

DEVELOPMENT OF AN ANALYTICAL MODEL FOR TUBULAR BRAIDED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Tubular braided composites (TBC) consist of woven fibers that are infused within a resin matrix. Braid preforms are created using a device known as a Maypole braider and can be manufactured with different weaving patterns (diamond, regular, or Hercules). Potential applications for TBC include: biomedical devices, sports equipment, aerospace, automotive, or architectural applications. Each of the aforementioned braid patterns will exhibit different characteristics which may be advantageous for specific design applications. Current models for TBC utilize a modified Classical Laminate Plate Theory (CLPT) method and are currently limited to only diamond braid patterns. A new, generalized analytical model has been developed which will allow for prediction of the mechanical properties of TBC for variety of braid patterns. The analytical model utilizes a volume average stiffness method in order to account for the effect of braid pattern on mechanical properties. The analytical model includes the following key parameters: braid pattern, braid angle, yarn geometry, and fiber/matrix material properties. The improved model will allow for the application of TBC to structural and medical industries and further research and development.

1 INTRODUCTION

Tubular braided composites (TBC) consist of braided yarns infused in a matrix. TBC are fabricated using a Maypole braider and can be manufactured with different braiding patterns. Braiding patterns include: diamond (one over- one under), regular (two over- two under), Hercules (three over- three under) and triaxial (diamond or regular with axial yarns) [1-5]. TBC can also be manufactured in open and closed mesh configurations [6-10]. The different braid patterns and braid configurations allows for TBCs to be applied to a wide range of applications.

Braided composites are an attractive manufacturing method over conventional composite laminates due to a high production rate, yarn interlacement and damage tolerance [11]. Due to these factors the use of braided composites is increasing in aerospace, sporting, automotive and marine industries [11-13]. Characterization of TBC is complicated by their non-uniform nature, variable constituents, and variable geometries. The material properties of TBC are commonly determined experimentally however this limits the implementation of TBC to specific applications [11].

Several models have been developed in order to predict the mechanical properties of TBC. The modeling approaches that are currently used for braided composites include: classical laminate plate theory (CLPT) based models [8, 9], finite element models (FEA) [13-16] and volume averaging models [11, 17-19]. Many of the braid models that exist are limited to single braid configurations. For example, the CLPT based models of Carey and Ayranci are limited to only diamond braided composites and the volume averaging method of Quek *et al* is limited to 2D triaxial braids. Several FEA studies have been performed on braided composites where varying braid configurations have

been considered [13, 16], however these models are computationally intensive and require specialized training and software to implement [11]. Many analytical, geometrical and finite element models exist for braided composites [8, 9, 11, 13, 15, 16], however a comprehensive analysis and comparison of the different possible braiding patterns has not been performed. Currently, a generalized analytical model does not exist specifically for tubular composite braids.

The aim of this work is to develop a generalized analytical model of TBC based on the geometrical and mechanical properties of tubular composite braids. A generalized analytical model will provide a powerful tool for the design and implementation of TBC. In addition, the model will also account for the micromechanical material properties of fiber and resin used to create the braid structure. The proposed model will utilize key braid parameters to provide a powerful design tool for TBC manufacturers since braids of varying geometry, fiber and matrix can be modeled. Since the material properties of composite braids can be easily predicted using this method this will allow for more widespread implementation of TBC.

2 Model Development

A new generalized model is presented in this paper for describing the mechanical properties of tubular braided composites. The model will be implemented by using micromechanical models to account for matrix and fiber contributions. Geometries of the tubular braid structures will be described using braid equations similar to Alpyildiz *et al* [20]. The braid equations allow for TBC to be represented using simple mathematical expressions which can be implemented into solid modeling programs to allow for the visualization and analysis of braid geometries. Finally, a volume averaging method will be used to account for the contribution of the clockwise and counter-clockwise yarns within the braid unit cell.

2.1 Micromechanics

In order to model the mechanical properties of TBC the mechanical properties of the braid fibers and matrix must be taken into account. The individual braid yarns are assumed to behave as a transversely isotropic material [5, 8, 9, 11]. The compliance matrix, $[S]$, for the braid yarns in the local coordinate system (I - 2 - 3) is shown in equation (1). The elastic constants shown in equation (1) were determined using micromechanical models [21-23]. The rule of mixtures equations were used to determine the longitudinal elastic modulus E_1 and major Poisson's ratio, ν_{12} . The Halpin-Tsai equations were used to determine the transverse elastic modulus E_2 and in-plane shear modulus G_{12} . Finally, semi-empirical models were used to determine the out of plane shear modulus G_{23} and out-of-plane shear modulus ν_{23} [9]. Since the yarns are assumed to be transversely isotropic $E_2 = E_3$ and $G_{12} = G_{13}$.

$$[S] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{E_2} & -\frac{\nu_{32}}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{13}}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_2} & \frac{1}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{23}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{13}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

2.2 Braided Composite Geometry

The geometry of TBC will be described using equations that take into account key braiding parameters such as braid angle (θ), yarn width (W_y), yarn thickness (a), mandrel diameter (D_0), and the number of braider bobbins (n). Example braid geometries for diamond, regular, and Hercules braided composites are shown in Figure 1. The fully parametric braid geometries shown in this figure were generated using a custom Python script and a computer aided design software package (Rhino 3D 5.0, Robert McNeel & Associates, Seattle, WA, USA) to visualize the three dimensional braid geometries.

Figure 1: Example braided composite geometries (a) diamond braid (b) regular braid (c) Hercules braid

The braid geometries shown in Figure 1 were determined from braid angle (θ), yarn width (W_y), yarn thickness (a), mandrel diameter (D_0), and the number of braider bobbins (N). The undulation length of braid yarns within a unit cell was determined based on the number of braider yarns (N), braid nominal radius (r_0) and braid angle (θ). The relationship between braid yarn shift angle (β) and undulation length is illustrated in Figure 2. The braid shift angle, β , shown in Figure 2 is related to half the total number of yarn carriers ($n = N/2$) used to fabricate the braid geometry. The equation shift angle equation is shown in equation (2).

Figure 2: Braid unit cell geometry

$$\beta = \frac{2\pi}{n} \quad (2)$$

In order to model the mechanical behavior of braided composites two coordinate system transformations are required. These coordinate system transformations are computed using geometric parameters of the composite braids. The coordinate system transformation in Figure 3 (a) is required in order to account for the undulation of the braid yarns and depends on the crimp angle (ϕ) of the braid yarns. The coordinate system transformation in Figure 3 (b) accounts for the braid angle (θ) of the clock-wise and counter-clockwise yarns.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Coordinate system transformations (a) Conversion from yarn coordinate system (1-2-3) to undulation coordinate system (x' - y' - z') (b) Conversion of undulation coordinate system (x' - y' - z') to global coordinate system (X - Y - Z).

The braid yarns were assumed to follow a sinusoidal path due to the repeating nature of the braiding process [5, 20, 24]. The equations for the braid yarns will be described in their local coordinate system (x' - y' - z'). This coordinate system is required since a coordinate system transformation will be required for the volume averaging method described in section 2.3.

The equation for a diamond braided composite is shown in equation (3). In this equation, L_{und} represents the length of one undulation of a braid yarn. The variable k represents the braid yarn period and the variable a represents the thickness of the braid yarn. The undulation height of the braid yarn is represented by the variable $h(x')$ and the position along the undulation length is represented using the variable x' .

$$L_{und} = \frac{r_0 \beta}{\sin \theta}, \quad k = \frac{2\pi}{L_{und}} \quad (3)$$

$$h(x') = \frac{a}{2} \sin(k \cdot x')$$

In addition the crimp angle of the braid yarns (ϕ) was determined along the braid yarn length. The braid yarn crimp angle was determined by computing the derivative of the braid yarn undulation height equation ($h(x')$). Determination of the braid yarn crimp angle is shown in (4). The braid yarn crimp angle is necessary for determining the mechanical properties of braided composites and for coordinate system transformation described in section 2.3.

$$\begin{aligned}\tan(\phi) &= \frac{dh(x')}{dx'} = \frac{a}{2} \cdot k \cdot \cos(k \cdot x') \\ m = \cos(\phi) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2(\phi)}} \\ n = \sin(\phi) &= \frac{\tan(\phi)}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2(\phi)}}\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

Equations for regular and Hercules braids were determined using similar equation to the sinusoidal diamond braid equation shown in equation (3). Equations for the undulation height of regular and Hercules braids are shown in (5) and (6). The difference between diamond, regular and Hercules braids is demonstrated in equations (5) and (6). The yarn crimp angle for regular and Hercules braids was computed in a similar manner to the diamond braid shown in equation (4). The undulation of the diamond, regular and Hercules braid patterns are compared in Figure 4.

$$\text{Regular Braid } h(x') = \begin{cases} \frac{a}{2}, & \text{if } 0 \leq x' \leq \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \\ -\frac{a}{2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi \cos(\alpha)x'}{r_0\beta} + \frac{\pi}{2}\right), & \text{if } \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \leq x' \leq 2 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \\ \frac{a}{2}, & \text{if } 2 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \leq x' \leq 3 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \\ \frac{a}{2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi \cos(\alpha)x'}{r_0\beta} + \frac{\pi}{2}\right), & \text{if } 3 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \leq x' \leq 4 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Hercules Braid } h(x') = \begin{cases} \frac{a}{2}, & \text{if } 0 \leq x' \leq \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \\ \frac{a}{2}, & \text{if } \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \leq x' \leq 2 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \\ \frac{a}{2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi \cos(\alpha)x'}{r_0\beta} + \frac{\pi}{2}\right), & \text{if } 2 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \leq x' \leq 3 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \\ -\frac{a}{2}, & \text{if } 3 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \leq x' \leq 4 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \\ -\frac{a}{2}, & \text{if } 4 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \leq x' \leq 5 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \\ -\frac{a}{2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi \cos(\alpha)x'}{r_0\beta} + \frac{\pi}{2}\right), & \text{if } 5 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \leq x' \leq 6 \cdot \frac{\beta}{2} \frac{r_0}{\cos(\alpha)} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Figure 4: Comparison of diamond, regular and Hercules braid yarn undulations in the undulation coordinate system (x' - y' - z')

2.3 Volume Average Stiffness Method

A volume averaging stiffness method has been utilized in order to determine the material properties of tubular braided composites. This method was selected since it allows for the mechanical properties of the wide variety of braid geometries shown in section 2.2 to be determined. The volume averaging stiffness method has been previously used to model the behavior of 2D triaxial braided composites [11, 17, 19] however, this method has not been generalized to account for the braid geometries shown in section 2.2.

The volume averaging method involves three main steps. First, a coordinate system transformation is performed to convert from the local yarn coordinate system ($1-2-3$) to the undulation coordinate system ($x'-y'-z'$). The local to undulation coordinate system transformation is illustrated in Figure 3 (a). This figure shows that the braid crimp angle, ϕ , is used to transform from the local coordinate system to the undulation coordinate system.

The transformation matrix used to convert from the local ($1-2-3$) coordinate system to the undulation ($x'-y'-z'$) coordinate system is shown in equation (7). The yarn crimp angle (ϕ) is determined by calculating the derivative of the braid yarn equations ((3), (5) and (6)) shown in section 2.2. The compliance matrix $[S'_{xyz}]$, shown in equation (8), in the undulation coordinate system is calculated by integrating over the yarn undulation length.

The second step in the volume averaging method is illustrated in Figure 3 (b) where a second coordinate system transformation is performed to convert from the undulation coordinate system ($x'-y'-z'$) to the global coordinate system ($X-Y-Z$). The transformation matrix $[T]$ to convert from the undulation to global coordinate system is shown in equation (9). In this equation the braid angle (θ) is

used determine the compliance matrix, $[S_{XYZ}]$, of each braid yarn in the global coordinate system. The calculation of the compliance matrix $[S_{XYZ}]$ is shown in equation (10).

$$[T'_{xyz}] = \begin{bmatrix} m^2 & 0 & n^2 & 0 & 2mn & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ n^2 & 0 & m^2 & 0 & -2mn & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & m & 0 & -n \\ -mn & 0 & mn & 0 & m^2 - n^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & n & 0 & m \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$m = \cos(\phi)$$

$$n = \sin(\phi)$$

$$[S'_{xyz}] = \frac{1}{L_{und}} \int_0^{L_{und}} [T'_{xyz}]^T [S] [T'_{xyz}] dx \quad (8)$$

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} c^2 & s^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2cs \\ s^2 & c^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -2cs \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c & s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -s & c & 0 \\ -cs & cs & 0 & 0 & 0 & c^2 - s^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$c = \cos(\theta)$$

$$s = \sin(\theta)$$

$$S_{XYZ} = [T]^T [S'_{xyz}] [T] \quad (10)$$

The final step in the volume averaging procedure accounts for the contributions of the clockwise and counter-clockwise braid yarns and, if present, axial yarns. The volume averaging equations for diamond, regular, and Hercules braid yarns are illustrated in Figure 6. The volume averaging method accounts for the contribution of the clockwise (θ^+) and counter-clockwise (θ^-) braid yarns. In addition, matrix only regions and axial yarns can also be accounted for. The final overall stiffness matrix $[C^G]$ for the braided composite is determined by computing the volume fraction of the clockwise ($V_{f\theta^+}$), counter-clockwise ($V_{f\theta^-}$) and excess matrix (V_m) within the braid unit cell. The equation for the overall stiffness matrix $[C^G]$ is shown in equation (11). Finally, the elastic constants for the tubular braided composites are determined from the global compliance matrix $[S^G]$ shown in equation (12). The determination of the elastic constants is shown in equation (13).

$$[C^G] = V_{f\theta^+} [C_{XYZ}^+] + V_{f\theta^-} [C_{XYZ}^-] + V_m [C_{XYZ}^m] \quad (11)$$

$$S^G = [C^G]^{-1} \quad (12)$$

$$E_x = \frac{1}{S^g_{11}}, E_y = \frac{1}{S^g_{22}}, E_z = \frac{1}{S^g_{33}} \quad (13)$$

$$G_{xy} = \frac{1}{S^g_{66}}, G_{yz} = \frac{1}{S^g_{44}}, G_{xz} = \frac{1}{S^g_{55}}$$

$$v_{xy} = \frac{-S_{12}^g}{S_{11}^g}, v_{zx} = \frac{-S_{13}^g}{S_{33}^g}, v_{yz} = \frac{-S_{23}^g}{S_{22}^g}$$

The prediction of the elastic constants of tubular braided composites was automated by creating a custom program (MATLAB, 2014a, The Math Works, Natick, MA) that automates the above volume averaging and geometrical analysis procedure. Using this method the effect of braid geometry or matrix and fiber material properties can be rapidly explored and can therefore be used as a design tool for manufacture tubular braided composites.

3 Model Results/ Predictions

The proposed model described in Section 2 will first be compared with existing models. The proposed model will also be validated experimentally. The model proposed by Ayranci and Carey [8] will be used for comparison with proposed model. This model was selected since all of the main braid geometry and mechanical properties were listed allowing for direct comparison between the two models. The mechanical properties of the impregnated yarns are listed in Table 1 and the braid geometry dimensions are listed in Table 2.

	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}
Kevlar 49- Epoxy experimental properties [8, 9, 25]	79.7	5.9	1.5	0.33

Table 1: Elastic Properties of Kevlar 49 yarns impregnated with Epon825/Ancamine1482 resin

Number of Carriers (N)	Yarn Width (W_y)-mm	Yarn Thickness (a)- mm	Mandrel Diameter (D_0)-mm
18	3.1	0.38	11.11

Table 2: Tubular braided composite braid dimensions. Braid geometry dimensions taken from Ayranci et al [8]

3.1 Comparison with Existing Models

Comparison of the proposed model with the CLPT-based diamond braid model of Ayranci and Carey is shown in Figure 7. Both models exhibit a decrease in longitudinal elastic modulus, E_{xx} , as braid angle, θ , increases. Additionally, the results of the in-plane shear modulus (G_{xy}) are compared in Figure 8. The mechanical properties and braid geometry parameters shown in Table 1 and Table 2 were used to compare the results from the two models.

Figure 5: Comparison of results of proposed model with the CLPT-based diamond braid model of Ayranci and Carey [8]

Figure 6: Comparison of shear modulus of proposed model with model results of Ayranci et al [7]

3.2 Effect of braid pattern on model prediction

The new braid model described in Section 2 is capable of modeling several common braid configurations. Three braid patterns were selected to demonstrate the effect of braid pattern on mechanical properties. The resulting elastic moduli (E_{xx} , E_{yy} and E_{zz}) for diamond, regular and Hercules braid patterns are shown in Figure 8. The mechanical and geometric properties shown in Table 1 and Table 2 were used for comparing the three braid patterns. For the comparison of the braid geometries the same fiber volume fraction (V_f) was used. The fiber volume fraction will be constant since the number of braid yarns (N) and yarn geometry (W_y and a) has been held constant. The results shown in Figure 8 allow for a direct comparison of the elastic moduli for the three braid patterns.

(a)

Figure 7: Effect of braid pattern on elastic moduli (a) diamond (b) regular (c) Hercules braid

4 Discussion

A new analytical model that predicts the elastic properties of tubular braided composites has been presented. The new generalized model allows for the prediction of elastic properties for varying braid patterns (diamond, regular and Hercules) and accounts for braid geometry during manufacturing. Previous studies have focused on the modeling of a specific braid pattern and as a result the direct comparison of different braid patterns is not possible.

The presented model has been compared with the results of a previous model for diamond braided composites. The results of this comparison show that the two models calculate similar longitudinal elastic moduli for a braid angle of 45° . The two models deviate for braid angles other than 45° . The model of Ayranci and Carey assumes that yarn undulation only occurs within defined regions within the braid unit cell. Braid yarns are assumed to be flat in the cross-over regions (where clockwise and counter-clockwise yarns overlap). This assumption will result in an over prediction of the longitudinal elastic modulus of a diamond braid since the braid yarn crimp angle is neglected in the cross-over regions. This results in a greater contribution of the braid yarns in the longitudinal direction in the cross-over regions.

The braid model of Ayranci and Carey also assumes that the braid unit cell geometry will exhibit symmetrical behavior as a function of braid angle (θ). This means that the braid unit cell height and width will vary proportionally as a braid angle changes. This assumption is not physically possible since the braid unit cell width ($W_{unitCell}$) is a constant value that will depend on the braid mandrel radius (r_0) and the number of braid yarns (n) used to fabricate the braid geometry.

$$W_{unitCell} = \frac{2\pi r_0}{n} \quad (14)$$

The braid unit cell width is independent of braid angle (θ) as shown in equation (14). The asymmetrical behavior of braid unit cells is also discussed by Ji *et al.* [13]. The asymmetry in the proposed model is demonstrated in Figure 7. In this figure, the model by Ayranci and Carey produces results for shear modulus which are symmetry about a braid angle of 45° whereas the current proposed model is not symmetric.

The comparison of the braid patterns shown in Figure 8 demonstrates the effect of braiding pattern on elastic moduli. This figure demonstrates that braiding patterns has an influence on mechanical properties. As an example, the resulting longitudinal elastic modulus (E_x) for a braid angle of 30° for the diamond, Regular and Hercules braids was found to be 9.86, 15.9 and 16.4 GPa, respectively. The difference in mechanical properties of the three braid patterns can be attributed to the geometry of the three patterns. The regular and Hercules braids exhibited greater mechanical properties than the diamond braid pattern. The difference in mechanical properties can be attributed to the effect of the crimp angle (ϕ) of the braid yarns. The effect of crimp angle is demonstrated in Figure 3. In this figure, it can be seen that fiber undulations are limited to specific regions for the regular and Hercules braids whereas undulation occur throughout the diamond braid strand path. Since the fiber undulations are more limited for regular and Hercules braids, this results in a greater contribution of the braid yarns to the in-plane elastic properties (E_x and E_y) than the diamond braid pattern.

5 Conclusion

A new generalized model has been developed for the evaluation of a variety of braid patterns. A custom Python script has been generated for the visualization of a variety of braid geometries as well, the analytical model has been implemented using a MATLAB script and allows for the effect of geometry on braided composites to be explored. This new analytical model will provide a useful design tool for the initial evaluation and selection of braiding patterns for specific applications.

In this work the new analytical model has been compared with the results of a previous model. Further comparison with experimental results will be required for complete model validation. Currently, there are very few studies that compare the effect of braid pattern, braid angle or braid geometry on mechanical properties. Therefore, a comprehensive experimental program is required in order to examine the effect of braid pattern and braid yarn geometry on mechanical properties. The proposed model has currently been implemented for biaxial braided composites. The newly developed model can also be extended to the modeling of braided composites with axial yarns (triaxial braids).

6 References

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